

ECER 2016 PROCEEDINGS AND REPORT [DELIVERABLE 3.1]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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DISCLAIMER

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document presents the preparations, description and proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Robotics (ECER) 2016, which took place from 11th to 15th April in Vienna, Austria.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

This document will be followed by two further deliverables (D3.2, D3.3) in WP3 that contain the proceedings of the ECER issues of 2017 and 2018. Furthermore, it is connected with D3.4, which will contain the final conference plan as outcome of the project ER4STEM.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

Section 2 describes the preparations for ECER 2016. Section 3 reports on the schedule and lists the participating teams. The results of ECER 2016 are presented in Section 4. The remaining sections give a summary and conclusion and provide a glossary as well as references. The Call for Papers for ECER 2016 is attached in Section 9. Furthermore, the student papers are attached in Section 10.

2 PREPARATIONS FOR ECER 2016

2.1 PHASES OF ORGANIZATION

The preparation phase was split into two phases: Phase 1 from September to December 2015 and Phase 2 from January to April 2016.

Performed tasks in Phase 1:

- Setup of ECER Website: A website was set up within the PRIA website for informing about the conference. It also included a form for allowing the registration of participants. Later, the Call for Papers was added and a link to a paper submission tool (Open conference tool) was provided.
- Finding sponsors: As ECER itself was covered by ER4STEM, the intention was to find sponsors that would support material costs of participating teams. E.g. two teams consisting only of girls from the Austrian technical high school denoted as Technologisches Gewerbemuseum (TGM) were supported by “genderfair”, a project by the Vienna University of Technology that tackles gender issues concerning university careers.
- Organisation of venue: The technical high school TGM was used as venue for hosting the ECER. It provides a large hall that was used for the tournaments as well as for the working places of the participants. Furthermore, one of the school’s lecture halls was used for the talks by the students and by researchers.
- Advertise participation: E-Mails were sent out to participants of previous issues of ECER. Also ER4STEM partners contacted their school partners to advertise for participation.
- Link to WP2: First planning of Botball workshop.

Performed tasks of Phase 2:

- Participation at Botball Instructors’ Summit at the KISS Institute of Practical Robotics (KIPR), Oklahoma, USA: Dr. Gotfried Koppensteiner of PRIA participated at the Botball Instructors’ Summit to obtain information about the season’s rules as well as about the current Botball set. Furthermore, details regarding the registration process and shipment of robotic sets to the participants were clarified.
- Delivery of Botball sets: PRIA arranged the delivery of Botball sets for all Austrian Botball teams as well as for the teams of Albania, Bulgaria and Belgium. The participating Botball teams of Egypt, Kuwait and Poland took care for their sets without support. Botball sets are required if a team wants to participate in the official Botball tournament. Each set comprises two robotics controllers, an iRobot by Create, as well as metal and Lego parts.
- Contact with participants: PRIA was in regular contact with the participants of ECER for supporting in various matters ranging from the writing of papers to technical issues with the robotics sets.
- Link to WP2: One Botball workshop at PRIA was prepared and carried out. Information from the Botball Instructors’ Summit was passed on to the Austrian teams. The Bulgarian teams received this information from PRIA in a separate workshop using a telepresence robot. The teams of Albania and Belgium paid the travel for a PRIA staff member for getting individual workshops.

- Planning of tournaments: Four tournaments were envisaged for ECER 2016:
 - Botball tournament: Botball is an educational robotics program that focuses on engaging middle and high school aged students in team-oriented robotics competitions. The Botball program has been active since 1998 and features a robotics curriculum which focuses on designing, building and programming a pair of autonomous robots. Teams use a standardized kit of materials and document the process. All materials in the kits are exactly the same for every team around the world, so there is no unfair advantages. Only Botball sets are allowed in this tournament and the game rules are provided by KIPR during the Botball Instructors' Summit. KIPR develops the annual rules in the time before this summit. The tournament at ECER represents the official European Championship in Botball.
 - Open tournament: The Open tournament uses the same rules and game table as in the Botball tournament. However, teams with any robotics set are allowed to participate.
 - Aerial tournament: This tournament does not require a game table but a setting for using drones. Accordingly other rules apply.
 - Underwater workshop/tournament: This trial workshop/tournament used a small 3D-printed submarine developed by a student employed by PRIA.
- Organisation of material for ECER: Three game tables were planned for ECER of which one was provided by PRIA (using ER4STEM funding). The other game tables were provided by two Austrian schools participating at ECER. Name tags and printed handouts for the ECER participants were prepared. Spare parts for Botball (in case material of participants breaks) were organised. T-shirts were designed that could be obtained by the participants. EU funding was promoted and visualized in advertising and information materials
- Organisation of invited talks: ECER was carried out in accordance with this year's issue of the International Conference on Robotics in Education (RiE). The RiE is a conference for researchers being active in the field of educational robotics. The RiE was established in 2010 in the frame of the EU project Centrobot and has been organised every year since then. As RiE 2016 was carried out in parallel to ECER 2016, the high school students were able to visit the sessions of RiE. Besides, two talks by researchers were organised specifically for ECER 2016. Moreover, a few talented high school students were invited to present their interesting work on robots and drones during two talks.
- Submission and review of student papers: 21 papers were submitted by high school students with some of them having sole authors and others by groups of authors. All papers were reviewed by at least two researchers and 12 papers were selected to be presented. The best 4 of these 12 papers were chosen to be presented in a special session at RiE in order to have also the actual researchers as audience.
- Detailed planning of ECER schedule: According to the accepted papers, the invited talks and the planned tournaments, the ECER schedule was created (see Section XY).
- Planning of staff: PRIA staff was planned for manning the registration desk as well as a support desk. Moreover PRIA employees acted as judges and fulfilled various other tasks during ECER.
- Preparation of invitation letters: The participants from Egypt and Kuwait needed Visa for entering Austria, which required invitation letters. Also an invitation letter was issued for the participants of Albania.

3 DESCRIPTION OF ECER 2016

3.1 SCHEDULE

The schedule was aligned with the lesson times of the venue. The schedule encompassed the following activities:

- Grey blocks: Practicing times for the participants
- Orange blocks: Tournaments (Botball, Open, Aerial)
- Light blue blocks: Underwater-Workshop/Tournament
- Black blocks: Talks by researchers and students, awards ceremony
- Green block: Teachers' conference/workshop of the ER4STEM project

	Monday, 11. April 2016	Tuesday, 12. April 2016	Wednesday, 13. April 2016	Thursday, 14. April 2016	Friday, 15. April 2016	
8:00-8:50	Registration (Exnersaal)	Registration (Exnersaal)		Registration for RIE (Aula EG)	PRIA-Open and KIPR-Aerial Open Practice	
8:50-9:40	Open Practice for Botball, Open, Aerial (Exnersaal)	Open Practice for Botball, PRIA-Open, KIPR-Aerial (Exnersaal)	Open Practice for Botball and Underwater (Exnersaal)	PRIA-Open and KIPR-Aerial Seeding Rounds (Exnersaal)	Welcome Introd. and Keynote Prof. Petrovic (HS 1)	
9:40-9:50						Onsite Presentations for Botball-Teams (H128 - PRIA-Lab)
9:50-10:40		Break	Student Talks 1 - Software Development and Autonomous Projects (HS1)	Student Talks 2 - Best Practices and Mechanical Engineering (HS 1)	Techn. Session 1 (9:50-10:40, HS1) Poster-Pres. 1 and Coffe-Break (10:40-11:10 CCNA-Room) Techn. Session 3 (11:10-12:20, HS1)	Techn. Session 5 (9:50-11:00, HS1) Techn. Session 6 (11:10-12:20, HS1)
10:40-11:30		Botball Open Practice (Exnersaal)	PRIA-Open and KIPR-Aerial Finals (Exnersaal)			
11:30-12:20						
12:20-12:30	Lunch / Break	Lunch / Break	Lunch / Break	Lunch / Break	Lunch / Break	
12:30-13:20						
13:20-14:10	Onsite Presentations for Botball-Teams (H128 - PRIA-Lab)	Botball Seeding Rounds (Exnersaal)	Botball - Double Elimination Rounds (Exnersaal)	ECER-Student Talks at RIE2016 (HS1)	Techn. Session 7 (HS1)	
14:10-15:00	Open Practice for Botball, Open, Aerial (Exnersaal)	Open Practice for PRIA-OPEN, KIPR-Aerial (Exnersaal)	Open Practice for KIPR-Aerial, Underwater, PRIA-Open (Exnersaal)	Techn. Session 3 (14:10-15:40, HS1) Poster-Pres. 2 and Coffee Break (15:40-16:00, CCNARoom)	Closing	
15:00-15:10	ER4STEM Teachers Conference (H744)			Open Practice for Botball (Exnersaal)	Botball Alliances and Finals (Exnersaal)	
15:10-16:00				Techn. Session 4 (HS 1)		
16:00-16:50						
16:50-17:00						
17:00-18:00					Awards Ceremony (HS1)	
18:05-18:40	Opening Ceremony, Dr. Gottfried Koppensteiner, Pria and Invited Talk, Prof. Pavel Petrovič Comenius University in Bratislava(HS1)	Invited Student Talks (HS1), Hovering Steward (HTL Rennweg) and RobBox 3.0 (Florian Kristof)		Christoph Krofitsch, PRIA "low-cost robotics controller hedgehog-lite" Reinhard Grabler, PRIA "underwater robotics" (HS1)		

3.2 PARTICIPANTS

ECER 2016 had participants from the following countries:

- Albania
- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Egypt
- Kuwait
- Poland

21 teams participated in the Botball competition having the following team names:

Tournament Team ID	Team Name	Country	Institution
BOTBALL	16-0188	ACE-Bots	Austria HTL Wiener Neustadt
	16-0191	Robo-SpabS	Austria TGM
	16-0192	Hearthbot	Austria HTBLVA Spengergasse
	16-0196	Orange	Austria Blum GmbH
	16-0239	TUES-България	Bulgaria Technological school "Electronic systems"
	16-0242	<i>theredhat</i>	Bulgaria ESICEE
	16-0270	Hayah International Academy	Egypt Hayah International Academy
	16-0375	Bot-Girls	Austria TGM
	16-0379	Antwerp International School	Belgium AIS Antwerp
	16-0385	Almighty 7	Austria HTBLVA Spengergasse
	16-0536	<i>Al ru'ya Bilingual School of Kuwait</i>	Kuwait Al ru'ya Bilingual School of Kuwait
	16-0596	Schmidis Armeem	Austria HTL Saalfelden
	16-0597	ProBot	Austria HTL Saalfelden
	16-0598	Technical Satisfaction	Austria HTL Saalfelden
	16-0599	Chaosbot	Austria HTL Hollabrunn
	16-0600	Scorp Robotics	Austria HTL Hollabrunn
	16-0602	items	Austria HTL Wiener Neustadt
	16-0603	robot0nfire	Austria HTL Wiener Neustadt
	16-0604	TeamAlbania	Albania HTL Shkodra
	16-0605	robotiX++;	Austria TGM
	16-0647	GG - The Franciszek Leja State School	Poland The Franciszek Leja State School

8 teams participated in the Open tournament:

Tournament Team ID	Team Name	Country	Institution
OPEN	PRIA-04	A-Team Bots	Austria HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PRIA-05	Private Void	Austria HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PRIA-06	Rainbo[w]ter	Austria HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PRIA-09	MiracleRobotics	Austria TGM
	PRIA-12	GG - Guest	Poland The Franciszek Leja State School
	PRIA-13	GG - Open	Poland The Franciszek Leja State School
	PRIA-14	GG - Open Youth	Poland The Franciszek Leja State School
	PRIA-15	KillerbyTHes meet MARDA	Austria Talentehaus

2 teams participated in the Aerial tournament:

Tournament Team ID	Team Name	Country	Institution
AERIAL	PRIA-01	<i>Hayah Aerial</i>	Egypt Hayah International Academy
	PRIA-11	GG - Aerial	Poland The Franciszek Leja State School

3 teams participated in the Underwater tournament:

Tournament Team ID	Team Name	Country	Institution
UNDERWATE	PRIA-07	Talentehaus MARDA	Austria Talentehaus
	PRIA-08	Team KillerbyTHes	Austria Talentehaus
	16-0604	TeamAlbania	Albania HTL Shkodra

Furthermore, as the International Conference on Robotics in Education (RiE) was hosted in parallel to ECER, the attendants of RiE had the chance to visit ECER. As a consequence, more than 40 international visitors from the following countries were present at ECER:

- Austria
- Bulgaria
- Czech Republic
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Israel
- Italy
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Russia
- Slovakia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Thailand
- UK

Furthermore, several classes from middle and primary schools of Vienna took the chance of visiting ECER. This allowed the young pupils to see possibilities of engagement in STEM and robotics in particular.

4 PROCEEDINGS OF ECER 2016

4.1 STUDENT PAPERS

21 papers were submitted by the Botball teams. They were reviewed by researchers (mostly PRIA staff) and 12 papers were chosen to be presented at ECER. The best 4 papers were chosen to be presented in a special session at RiE so that the high school students had the possibility to show their work also to the international researchers attending RiE. The other 8 papers were chosen to be presented during the student paper sessions at ECER on Tuesday and Wednesday.

Papers of the student session at RiE:

- HTL Saalfelden, Austria: “Mechanical jigs and fixtures – Solutions for more reliability and accuracy”
- HTL Wr. Neustadt, Austria: “fI0w – a Workflow Optimisation Tool”
- HTL Wr. Neustadt, Austria: “Remote Monitoring and Controlling of Robotics Systems with MissionControl”
- Hayah International Academy, Egypt: “A Study of the Botball Kit and Suggestions of Improvement”

Papers of the session on Tuesday:

- TGM Wien, Austria: “Bot-Ball”
- HTL Saalfelden, Austria: “Sensors in engineering”
- HTL Saalfelden, Austria: “Machine Learning for BotBall”
- TalenteNhaus NÖ, Austria: “Photovoltaic plants – Energy to Infinity”

Papers of the session on Wednesday:

- HTL Spengergasse, Austria: “Hacking the Wallaby”
- HTL Hollabrunn, Austria: “Evaluation of improving parts for a gripper”
- TGM Wien, Austria: “Robot – Programming, Assembling and Implementation of Ideas”
- Antwerp International School, Belgium: “3d Printing – Advancing industry one layer at a time”

For the evening talk session on Tuesday, two contributions by high school students were invited. A group of 5 high school students presented their work on a drone usable for serving customers in a restaurant. The title of their talk was “Hovering Stewart – the flying waiter”. Afterwards a humanoid robot was introduced by high school student Florian Kristof in his talk “RobBox 3.0”.

4.2 TALKS GIVEN BY RESEARCHERS

On Monday after the opening ceremony, Assistant Professor Dr. Pavel Petrovic of Comenius University in Bratislava gave a talk entitled “Lessons Learned from 20 years of Robotics Competitions”.

On Thursday, the ECER participants had the chance of visiting the RiE sessions. Moreover, two talks by university students employed by PRIA were given in the evening talk session to show the possibilities of research during university studies. Christoph Krofitsch gave a talk entitled “Hedgehog” concerned with a low-cost robotics controller and Reinhard Grabler introduced the model used for the underwater workshop in this talk “Underwater Robotics”.

4.3 TOURNAMENT RESULTS

4.3.1 BOTBALL

A team’s overall score for the Botball tournament was composed of three equal parts:

- Score achieved in the seeding rounds
- Score of the documentation (including the paper)
- Achieved rank in Double Elimination

Team Name	Seeding		Documentation		Double Elimination		Overall	
	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank
items	0,950647249	1	0,9675	4	1,000	1	2,918147249	1
robotOnfire	0,950647249	1	0,968	3	0,952	2	2,871028202	2
Orange	0,826235658	3	0,9485	5	0,714	7	2,489021372	3
Schmidis Armee	0,598043542	7	0,9975	1	0,810	5	2,405067352	4
ProBot	0,544535157	8	0,7575	11	0,905	3	2,206797062	5
ACE-Bots	0,780413357	4	0,788	9	0,61904762	9	2,187460976	6
Technical Satisfaction	0,632943513	6	0,69	13	0,810	5	2,132467322	7
GG - The Franciszek Leja State Scho	0,730141218	5	0,464	20	0,857	4	2,051284075	8
Hayah International Academy	0,385113269	12	0,9875	2	0,619	9	1,991660888	9
Scorp Robotics	0,456935863	10	0,6625	15	0,619	9	1,738483483	10
TeamAlbania	0,208590762	17	0,791	8	0,714	7	1,713876476	11
robotX++;	0,419608708	11	0,6695	14	0,619	9	1,708156327	12
Almighty 7	0,281626949	15	0,9445	6	0,429	13	1,654698378	13
Bot-Girls	0,246726979	16	0,805	7	0,429	13	1,480298407	14
Robo-SpabS	0,385113269	12	0,6385	18	0,42857143	13	1,452184697	15
theredhat	0,491431303	9	0,6595	16	0,238	17	1,389026541	16
TUES-България	0,385113269	12	0,6395	17	0,238	17	1,262708507	17
Al ru'ya Bilingual School of Kuwait	0,13838629	19	0,781	10	0,238	17	1,157481528	18
Hearthbot	0,13838629	19	0,747	12	0,238	17	1,123481528	19
Antwerp International School	0,173286261	18	0,5545	19	0,238	17	0,965881499	20
Chaosbot	0,068181818	21	0,2825	21	0,429	13	0,779253247	21

4.3.2 OPEN

A team's overall score for the Open tournament was composed of two equal parts:

- Score achieved in the seeding rounds
- Achieved rank in Double Elimination

Team Name	Seeding		Double Elimination		Overall	
	Score	Rank	Score	Rank	Score	Rank
Private Void	0,879934211	2	1,000	1	1,879934211	1
A-Team Bots	0,993421053	1	0,875	2	1,868421053	2
Rainbo[w]ter	0,533599624	4	0,750	3	1,283599624	3
KillerbyTHes meet MARDA	0,729793233	3	0,250	7	0,979793233	4
MiracleRobotics	0,320723684	6	0,625	4	0,945723684	5
GG - Guest	0,219454887	7	0,500	5	0,719454887	6
GG - Open Youth	0,421992481	5	0,250	7	0,671992481	7
GG - Open	0,121005639	8	0,500	5	0,621005639	8

4.3.3 AERIAL

A team's overall score was calculated as the mean value of the scores of the best three rounds of that team.

Team ID	Team Name	Day 1				Day 2				Total Score	Rank			
		Round 1	Round 2	Round 3	Round 4	Round 5	Round 6	Round 7	Round 8			Round 9	Round 10	Round 11
PRIA-11	GG - Aerial	25,00	70,00	0,00	18,75	11,25	35,00	25,00	25,00	31,50	25,00	123,50	76,17	1
PRIA-01	Hayah Aerial	0,00	18,75	25,00	0,00	25,00	25,00	10,00	25,00	12,50	10,00	0,00	25,00	2

4.3.4 UNDERWATER

A team's score was based on the amount of points scored in the tournament round.

Team Name	Score	Rank
Team KillerbyTHes	30	1
TeamAlbania	10	2
Talentehaus MARDA	10	2

5 SUMMARY

This deliverable describes activities during preparation of the ECER 2016. Also it presents the results and outcomes of ECER 2016.

6 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK – ECER 2017

This deliverable reports on the preparation and implementation of ECER 2016. In this context, it is also usable as a guidance for future issues of ECER as well as other conferences that take the ECER concept as basis.

7 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

ECER	European Conference on Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for STEM
HTL	Höhere Technische Lehranstalt (engl.: technical high school)
KIPR	KISS Institute of Practical Robotics
RiE	International Conference on Robotics in Education
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TGM	Technologisches Gewerbemuseum

8 BIBLIOGRAPHY

No references in this document.

9 CALL FOR PAPERS

ECER 2016

5th European Conference on Educational Robotics

CALL FOR PAPERS

TOPICS

Help to improve Botball or present other ideas and projects

Autonomous Projects: Have you done a technology related (research) project? Do you have good ideas how to organize Botball at your school? Tell us about it!

Mechanical Engineering: Do you have good ideas for new parts for the Botball Kit 2016, made of metal or 3D-printed? Explain us your ideas and underline them with 3D CAD Models in your paper!

Software Development: How to use sensors? We do have a strong interest in advanced sensor usage, e.g. for path planning. Do you have other good ideas or implemented some interesting functions?

Best Practices in Botball 2016: Do you have an outstanding mechanical design or a code segment worth explaining it in order to help improving the skills of the European teams?

Structure Papers as follows

- Abstract
- Introduction
- (• State-of-the-Art/Literature Review)
- Concept/Design
- Implementation
- Results/Conclusion

PAPERS

Templates and submission

Use our paper template in LaTeX or Word format for your entries (download: www.pria.at/user/). Submit your papers as PDF via Submission-System

>> <http://submission16.pria.at/> <<

Submission Deadline:

Mar 18, 2016 (11:59 p.m., UTC+1)

Notification of Acceptance: **Mar 30, 2016**

Final Submission Deadline: **Apr 8, 2016**

For the submission, a manuscript should be of maximum 5 pages. All papers undergo a review process.

A selected number of papers will be carefully chosen by the program committee for interactive multimedia presentation. The presentation should be up to 10 minutes long and will be followed by a 5 min Q&A. The accepted papers will be available on the conference website. **The achieved paper score will be counted to the documentation score with a valuation of 50%. When accepted for presentation, the paper must be presented properly for adding the achieved paper score to the documentation score**

Calculation: Documentation-Score

$$\text{DocScore} = [\text{DocScoreBotball} + \text{PaperScore}] / 2$$

(score between 0 and 1)

10 PRINTED PROCEEDINGS

ECER 2016

5th European Conference on Educational Robotics

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

TGM, Vienna

April 11 - 15

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Overview

Botball

The Botball Educational Robotics Program engages middle and high school aged students in a team-oriented robotics competition based on American education standards. By designing, building, programming, and documenting their robots, students reinforce their learning skills.

For more information about the American Botball Season see the Botball Webpage (www.botball.org)

ECER

The ECER is the venue for all teams of the European Botball region. Student teams pit their robots head-to-head in a fast paced, non-destructive regional tournament. Students as well as their teachers give talks about robots, their experience with Botball - but also can follow interesting researchers talks. The tournament is similar to the official Botball tournament in the USA. The Open Tournament has a different format.

See Schedule for details.

GCER

The GCER features the International Botball Tournament. Each year students, teachers, robotics enthusiasts, and professionals from around the world gather for the annual Global Conference on Educational Robotics. Students and teachers give presentations and exchange ideas on topics that range from curriculum integration to technical aspects of robotics. Professional speakers provide inspiration and insight into their robotics-related topics of expertise. The Global Conference features the International Botball Tournament, as well as the Beyond Botball Challenge for adults.

Botball Workshop 2016, tgm

Austria

In season 2015, the European Botball Workshop was held in tgm (Vienna Institute of Technology) in Austria. 18 teams and 110 participants attended a three day workshop and learned a lot of about robotics and program.

www.tgm.ac.at

The European Botball Season

The Botball season starts with the PRIA-Season Kick-Off in Vienna. This event is followed by team building and registration for participation activities.

During the three-day development workshop, which is held after the winter holidays, teams will receive their complete

reusable Botball® robotics kit. Teams will also learn about current robotics technology by participating in a variety of interactive exercises and activities. The hands-on workshop covers basic robot elements, processors, sensors, motors, programming, feedback and control, robot construction and Botball® game rules for the

current season. No previous experience with robots or programming is required!

After the workshop, teams have about ten weeks to develop their robots for tournament. In this time, they need also to document their development in English and submit three separate reports for review

About PRIA

Our vision is to prepare and motivate next generations of researchers, engineers, and scientists and to be the first address in educational robotics in Europe.

Dr. Gottfried Koppensteiner

Practical Robotics Institute Austria (PRIA) is a non-profit association with the aim to promote scientific and technical excellence in schools using robotics and ICT. PRIA provides a program with activities for students from primary, middle and

high school as well as for those attending university. In principle, PRIA merges the fields of research and education integrating the achievements and findings from research in education offering multiple possibilities for young people to become

acquainted with Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). PRIA activities encompassing workshops, camps, events, followed by competitions, research projects, and finalized with the thesis, mentoring and employment.

Our Activities

In Education

- Increase the interest of children and adolescents in science, technology and innovation
- Reduce skepticism towards technology
- Involve pupils and students into complex projects and problem solving processes
- Development of new teaching methods, which stimulate learning and experimenting as well as realizing one's own ideas
- Encouragement of entrepreneurial thinking

In Research

- Innovative control architectures for robotics and industrial automation
- Knowledge-based systems and agent technology for the automation of flexible industrial processes
- Augmented Reality to make visualization of industrial processes more efficient and easier to understand

Our Impact

PRIA's impact is significantly rising from year to year. In 2015 more than 1050 children and adolescents were reached by the activities carried out by PRIA. 35% of them were girls and 33% had migration background. Due to the funded projects, 80% were able to participate without costs. Additionally, nearly 400 parents were also reached as they represent an important part in the decisions of the children and adolescents regarding education and career.

About RiE

The 7th International Conference on Robotics in Education (RiE) is aimed at the presentation and discussion of the latest results and methods in the fields of research and development in Educational Robotics. Researchers are brought together that work on new applications, the latest products, or systems and components for using robotics in schools, in universities and in informal education. The objective is to provide an insight into the state-of-the-art of Educational Robotics to participants from both academic and school education.

All accepted papers that meet the requirements and standards of Springer will be published as a special volume in the prestigious Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing Series. The proceedings will be available via the SpringerLink digital library. The volumes of this series are submitted for inclusion to the leading indexing services including ISI Proceedings, EI-Compendex, DBLP, SCOPUS, Google Scholar and Springerlink. For more Information about the book series and about indexing visit Springer website: <http://www.springer.com/series/11156>.

RiE conferences have a history of previous successful editions due to the continuously growing interest in Educational Robotics in Europe and world-wide. RiE conferences count so far 6 editions; in Bratislava (2010), Vienna (2011), Prague (2012), Lodz (2013), Padua (2014), and Yverdon-les-Bains (2015).

The conference will include plenary sessions, contributed paper sessions and exhibits. The final program will be the result of a highly selective review process designed to include the best work of its kind in every category. Video presentations are recommended when they help presenters to offer a better understanding of robots, experiments and technical or educational practices. We expect an exciting conference programme, and cordially invite researchers and educators from the field of Educational Robotics to submit their papers.

ECER Scheduling

Monday, 11. April 2016		
8:00-8:50	Registration	Exnersaal
8:50-12:20	Open Practice (Botball, Open, Aerial)	Exnersaal
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20-18:00	Open Practice (Botball, Open, Aerial)	Exnersaal
15:10-18:00	ER4STEM Teachers Conference	H244
18:05-18:40	Opening Ceremony, Dr. Gottfried Koppensteiner	HS1
18:05-18:40	Pria and Invited Talk, Prof. Pavel Petrovič Comenius University in Bratislava	HS1
Tuesday, 12. April 2016		
8:00-8:50	Registration	Exnersaal
8:00-11:30	Open Practice (Botball, Open, Aerial)	Exnersaal
8:50-11:30	Onsite Presentations (Botball)	PRIA Lab H129
8:50-11:30	Underwater-Workshop and Open Practitce	HS2
11:30-12:20	Student Talks 1 - Software Development and Autonomous Projects	HS1
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20-18:00	Botball Seeding Rounds	Exnersaal
13:20-18:00	Open Practice for PRIA-OPEN, KIPR-Aerial	Exnersaal
13:20-18:00	Underwater-Workshop and Open Practitce	HS2
18:05-18:40	Invited Student Talks - Hovering Steward (HTL Rennweg)	HS1
18:05-18:40	Invited Student Talks - RobBox 3.0 (Florian Kristof)	HS2
Wednesday, 13. April 2016		
8:00-11:30	Open Practice for Botball and Underwater	Exersaal
8:00-11:30	PRIA-Open and KIPR-Aerial Seeding Rounds	Exersaal
13:20-15:10	Onsite Presentations (Botball)	PRIA Lab H129
11:30-12:20	Student Talks 2 - Best Practices and Mechanical Engineering	HS1
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20-18:00	Botball - Double Elimination Rounds	Exnersaal
13:20-18:00	Open Practice for KIPR-Aerial, Underwater, PRIA-Open	Exnersaal
Thursday, 14. April 2016		
8:00-12:20	Open Practie for KIPR-Aerial, PRIA-Open and Underwater	Exnersaal
08:00-8:50	Registration for RiE	Aula EG
8:50-9:50	Welcome Introd. and Keynote Prof. Petrovic´	HS1
9:50 - 10:40	Techn. Session 1	HS1
10:40-11:10	Poster-Pres. 1 and Coffe-Break	CCNA-Room
11:10-12:20	Techn. Session 2	HS1
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20-14:10	ECER-Student Talks at RiE2016	HS1
14:10-18:00	Open Practie for Botball	Exnersaal
14:10-15:40	Techn. Session 3	HS1
15:40-16:00	Poster-Pres. 2 and Coffe-Break	CCNA-Room
16:00-18:00	Techn. Session 4	HS1
18:05-18:40	Christoph Krofitsch, PRIA "low-cost robotics controller hedgehog-lite"	HS1
18:05-18:40	Reinhard Grabler, PRIA "underwater robotics"	HS1
Friday, 15. April 2016		
8:00-8:50	PRIA-Open and KIPR-Aerial Open Practice	Exnersaal
8:50-12:20	Botball Open Practice	Exnersaal
8:50-12:20	PRIA-Open and KIPR-Aerial Finals	Exnersaal
8:50-9:40	Keynote DI Lammer	HS1
9:50-11:00	Techn. Session 5	HS1
11:10-12:20	Techn. Session 6	HS1
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20-16:50	Botball Alliances and Finals (Exnersaal)	Exnersaal
13:20-15:00	Techn. Session 7	HS1
15:00-15:10	RIE Closing	HS1
17:00-18:00	Awards Ceremony	HS1

RIE Scheduling

Thursday, 14. April 2016		
08:00-8:50	Registration for RIE	Aula EG
8:50-9:50	Welcome Introd. and Keynote Prof. Petrovic´	HS1
9:50 - 10:40	Technical Session 1: Overview on Educational Robotics	HS1
10:40-11:10	Poster-Pres. 1 and Coffe-Break	CCNA-Room
11:10-12:20	Technical Session 2: Workshops, Activities and Curricula #1	HS1
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20-14:10	ECER Session	HS1
14:10-15:40	Technical Session 3: Controllers, Platforms and Tools	HS1
15:40-16:00	Poster-Pres. 2 and Coffe-Break	CCNA-Room
16:00-18:00	Technical Session 4: Integration with other Science Domains	HS1
19:00	Conference Dinner	
Friday, 15. April 2016		
8:50-9:40	Keynote DI Lammer	HS1
9:50-11:00	Technical Session 5: Workshops, Activities and Curricula #2	HS1
11:10-12:20	Technical Session 6: Human-Robot Interaction	HS1
12:20-13:20	Lunch / Break	
13:20:14:45	Technical Session 7: Simulation Environments and Robotics	HS1
14:45-15:00	RIE Closing	HS1

Committees

General Chair

Dr. Gottfried Koppensteiner

Publication Chair

Dipl.-Ing. Wilfried Lepuschitz

Educational Chair

Erhard List BSc.

Educational Chair

Lisa Vittori

PRIA Staff

Reinhard Grabler	(underwater)
Clemens Koza	(head judge)
Christoph Krofitsch	(head judge)
Timon Höbert	(technical support)
Andrej Gall	(technical support)
Martin Wolff	(technical support)
Nicole Weinert	(technical support)
Alvaro Lobato	(judge)
Tamara Reitprecht	(registration)
Lisamarie Schuster	(technical Support)
Markus Klein	(aerial judge)
Christoph Hackenberger	(aerial judge)
Carina Dolacek	

Assistant Professor Dr. Pavel Petrovič

Speech

April 11, 2016
6.05pm - 6.40pm

About

Comenius University in Bratislava,
Slovakia

Lessons Learned from 20 years of Robotics Competitions

Competitions are very motivational drive to cultivate interests in robotics and technology in general. Participation is usually rewarding, encourages fast and intensive learning, and it is a lot of fun as well. In this talk we will discuss experiences from various types of robotics contests, from the point of view of participants, team coaches, and organizers. We will show some interesting methods in Artificial Intelligence that we used in outdoor delivery robotic contest.

Short Biography

Pavel Petrovič has been a constructionist educator since he was 14. Starting as an instructor in summer electronics camp in Slovakia that he joined for more than 10 times, teaching informatics in secondary schools with LEGO Dacta in 90s, using LEGO robots in his doctoral dissertation in Artificial Intelligence at NTNU in Trondheim, running LEGO robotics activities with Scandinavian children in a summer camp CyberCamp in Trondheim for more than 5 times, building robots with children in robotics clubs in Norway and Slovakia, and lately also with his bachelor and master students in Future Technolo-

gies Laboratory at Comenius University in Bratislava. Pavel brought to Slovakia FLL competition in 2008, currently featuring 78 teams in the season of 2015 as well as RoboCup Junior, where he has been the head of jury for 15 years. He also designs tasks for a creative contest that is part of RoboCup Junior event, and currently he's organizing the 4th year of on-line robotics competition Summer League that complements FLL during the spring season. Meanwhile he teaches programming, software engineering and AI algorithms for robotics at Comenius University.

Reinhard Grabler

Underwater Robotics

Underwater robotics is a growing field due to the wide range of meaningful applications such as monitoring and sustaining the marine environment, detecting leaks in underwater pipes, data collection or search-and-rescue missions. Also the educational effect of underwater robotics should be pointed out. Besides gaining engineering skills due to the interdisciplinary characteristics, the interest of young people for the marine environment can be raised. By using the Hedgehog Light robotics controller and 3D printing technology it was possible to develop a robot for basic underwater applications.

Short Biography

Reinhard Grabler was born in 1991 in Korneuburg. After graduation at the TGM (Vienna Institute of Technology; Department of Information Technology, Internet- and Mediatechnology) in 2010 and after completing the military service he started his bachelor studies Mechanical Engineering – Economics on Vienna University of

Technology. From October 2011 to June 2013 he has been an research assistant at the Institute of Automation and Control at Vienna University of Technology. Since the founding of PRIA in April 2012 he was research assistant there, and is currently pausing work to finish studies.

Speech

April 14, 2016
6.05pm - 6.40pm

About

Practical Robotics Institute Austria

www.pria.at

Christoph Krofitsch

Speech

April 12 2015
6.05pm - 6.40pm

About

Practical Robotics Institute Austria

www.pria.at

Hedgehog

The field of robotics is very diverse and has various applications, especially in educational, research and home sections. It is the perfect tool for drawing interests of young people in areas of technology and science, not least because it uses current technology and connects theory and practice. There are many applications in science and research as well. Nevertheless, we think that robotics is underrepresented in mentioned fields – there are some solutions and products, however, most of them are very application specific, complicated and expensive. It's time for a simple, consistent and universal robotics system.

To use a smartphone as robot controller, some additional hardware that enables connecting and controlling robot components such as sensors, motors and servos is required. That hardware (mentioned as Low-Level Control, LLC) and the smartphone (mentioned as High-Level Control, HLC) are connected and share information. Hedgehog consists of three

core components which are responsible for different tasks. The LLC consists of two components: The Hardware Controller connects and controls robot components, holds the battery and manages the connection to the smartphone. The Software Controller saves and executes user-defined programs, which means it contains the robot's logic. On the other side there is the HLC consisting of the smartphone, where software libraries do the communication with the LLC and include built-in sensors like accelerometer, camera, etc. An App named Hedgehog Control Center is the interface to the user, enabling robot testing by accessing sensors, motors and servos, as well as developing programs that get downloaded to the Software Controller and get executed. Any communication is adhering to the AXCP and AXDP protocols that have been specified by us.

Short Biography

Christoph Krofitsch, BSc

Christoph Krofitsch was born in 1992 in Vienna. After completing elementary and secondary school in 1998 to 2006, he attended the Vienna Institute of Technology (TGM Wien) from 2006 to 2011. In this time he has done summer jobs at IT companies and executed several IT projects within the scope of project management class, including a printing controller with ID-card based authentication. In his last year he developed an knowledge-based robot control software within the scope of the Disbotics research project. After graduating with distinction at the Vienna Institute

of Technology, he started studying computer engineering at the Technical University of Vienna. Based on his diploma thesis from the Vienna Institute of Technology and the resulting paper (see below), he worked as research fellow at the Technical University of Vienna from October 2011 to May 2012. Since July 2012 to May 2013, he works as project assistant and tutor at the ACIN (Automation and Control Institute) at the Vienna University of Technology. In April 2012 he co-founded PRIA. Since June 2013 he works as AndriX project manager.

Hovering Steward - the flying waiter

Markus Kaiser (Projektleiter)
Christina Bornberg
Katharina Joksch
Alexander Punz
Lucas Ullrich

The wider context surrounding our topic is the invention of an innovative logistics system which will be deployed in the gastronomy business by using a multicopter.

The primary aim of the project is the development of a feasibility study which shows a possible way to originate an automatic flying waiter/waitress. Additionally a digital menu should be a further step to an automatic system. As an optional goal an event to test and apply the system will be organized.

To achieve the objectives of the project a comprehensive research phase was car-

wried out. First, similar existing systems had to be found to furthermore analyze them to get a better overview what technologies can be used. Second, a concept for each technology which was chosen for the project had to be worked out. Finally, each concept ran through a test process to ensure its functionality.

Considering all its advantages and drawbacks, we may conclude that this project contains of a variety of different components which have to work together perfectly to create a proper working system.

RobBox 3.0

Florian Kristof

What is important if someone wants to build a humanoid robot? This paper will list the sensors, motors, etc. which I used

for building my robot. Moreover it discusses why I prefer some kinds of sensors.

Student Paper Presentations

Papers in Session: ECER Students at RiE

Titel	Authors	Institution
Mechanical jigs and fixtures – Solutions for more reliability and accuracy	Patrick Bachmann, Markus Embacher Philip Trauner, Christoph Heiss, Nico	HTL Saalfelden, Austria
fI0w - a Workflow Optimisation Tool	Kratky, Nico Leidenfrost, Sebastian Schaffler, Christine Zeh, Sascha Zemann	HTL Wr. Neustadt, Austria
Remote Monitoring and Controlling of Robotic Systems with MissionControl	Daniel Swoboda, Raphael Weinfurter, Markus Pinter, Florian Ungersböck, Christoph Käferle, Daniel Honies	HTL Wr. Neustadt
A Study of the Botball Kit and Suggestions for Improvement	Alia ElKattan	Hayah International Academy, Egypt

Papers in Session 1: Software Development and Autonomous Projects

Titel	Authors	Institution
Bot-Ball	Christina Grasl; Manuela Gross; Hera Muhammad; Katharina Schöllerl	TGM Wien, Austria
Sensors in engineering	Michael Rest	HTL Saalfelden, Austria
Machine Learning for BotBall	Aleksandar Jevtic, Bernhard Vorhofer	HTL Saalfelden, Austria
Photovoltaic plants – Energy to Infinity	Viktoria Zach	Talentehaus NÖ, Austria

Papers in Session 2: Best Practices and Mechanical Engineering

Titel	Authors	Institution
Hacking the Wallaby Evaluation of improving parts for a gripper	Julian Palmanshofer, Julius Pürzelmayer, Manuel Reinsperger, Lukas Rysavy	HTL Spengergasse, Vienna, Austria
Paper ROBOT – PROGRAMMING, ASSEMBLING AND IMPLEMENTATION OF IDEAS	Mathias Bayer, Daniel Kaltenböck Andjela Arnautovic, Sarah Breit, Barbara Wiedermann, Julia Pöschl	HTL Hollabrunn, Austria TGM Wien, Austria
3d Printing - Advancing industry one layer at a time	Hannah Mcculloch	Antwerp International School, Belgium

List of Participating Teams

	ID	Team Name	Land	Institution
<i>Botball</i>	16-0270	<i>Hayah International Academy</i>	<i>Ägypten</i>	<i>Hayah International Academy</i>
	16-0379	Antwerp International School	Belgien	AIS Antwerp
	16-0239	TUES-България	Bulgarien	ESICEE
	16-0242	theredhat	Bulgarien	ESICEE
	16-0536	<i>Al ru'ya Bilingual School of Kuwait</i>	<i>Kuwait</i>	<i>Al ru'ya Bilingual School of Kuwait</i>
	16-0196	Orange	Österreich	Blum GmbH
	16-0192	Hearthbot	Österreich	HTBLVA Spengergasse
	16-0385	Almighty 7	Österreich	HTBLVA Spengergasse
	16-0599	Chaosbot	Österreich	HTL Hollabrunn
	16-0600	Scorp Robotics	Österreich	HTL Hollabrunn
	16-0596	Schmidis Armee	Österreich	HTL Saalfelden
	16-0597	ProBot	Österreich	HTL Saalfelden
	16-0598	Technical Satisfaction	Österreich	HTL Saalfelden
	16-0188	ACE-Bots	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	16-0602	items	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	16-0603	RobotOnFire	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	16-0191	Robo-SpabS	Österreich	TGM
	16-0375	Bot-Girls	Österreich	TGM
	16-0605	robotiX++;	Österreich	TGM
	16-0647	GG	<i>Polen</i>	<i>The Franciszek Leja State School</i>
	16-0604	TeamAlbania	Albanien	HTL Shkodra
PRIA Aerial	PA-0001	Hayah Aerial	Ägypten	Hayah International Academy
	PA-0002	AIRmazing	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PA-0003	GG - Aerial	Polen	The Franciszek Leja State School
PRIA Open	PO-0001	A-Team Bots	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PO-0002	Private Void	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PO-0003	Rainbo[w]ter	Österreich	HTL Wiener Neustadt
	PO-0004	MiracleRobotics	Österreich	TGM
	PO-0005	Schweder 3CHIT	Österreich	TGM
	PO-0006	GG - Guest	Polen	The Franciszek Leja State School
	PO-0007	TeamAlbania	Albanien	HTL Shkodra
	PO-0008	GG - Open	Polen	The Franciszek Leja State School
	PO-0009	GG - Open Youth	Polen	The Franciszek Leja State School
	PO-0010	Talentehaus MARDA	Österreich	Talentehaus
	PO-0011	Team KillerbyTHes	Österreich	Talentehaus
PRIA Under	PU-0001	Talentehaus MARDA	Österreich	Talentehaus
	PU-0002	Team KillerbvTHes	Österreich	Talentehaus

Directions

